

not involve any lengthy procedure of solvent extraction. The new reagent is more suitable for comparatively higher concentration of mercury.

References

1. J. W. MOORE and E. A. MOORE, "Environmental Chemistry", Academic Press Inc., New York., 1976, p. 397.
2. S. CHILOV, *Talanta*, 1973, **22**, 205.
3. T. T. GORSUCH, *Analyst*, 1959, **84**, 135; M. VANCOS and A. GERMAN, *Renta. Chem.*, 1968, **19**, 58.

Heats of Formation and Lattice Energies of Morpholine and Dioxan Complexes of Cobalt, Nickel, Copper and Zinc Fluoborates

AMITAVA CHATTERJI

St. Xavier's College, Ranchi

Manuscript received 4 October 1978, revised 19 February 1979,

accepted 12 March 1979

HEATS of formation and lattice energies of picoline complexes of copper fluoborate have been already reported¹. In this note heats of formation and lattice energies of morpholine and dioxan complexes of Co, Ni, Cu and Zn fluoborates have been determined. The isolation and characterisation of these complexes have been already reported²⁻³.

Fluoborate salts have been selected because the BF_4^- itself has got a tendency to take part in coordination and i.r. spectra study shows that BF_4^- serves as a bridge in the case of morpholine complex of cobalt².

In each case three readings were taken and the mean has been reported. Heats of formation (Q) determined by applying⁴ Hess's law of heat summation are given in the Table 1.

Calculation of Lattice Energy—Of the available equations⁵ for the calculation of lattice energy that of Kapustiniskii⁵ was found simple. But in these cases the values of ν (distance between the centre of the central cation and that of the co-ordinating atom) were not found in the literature and so the values of r_c (radii of the complex cations) and E_s (co-ordination energy) could not be calculated. Biltz and Grim⁶ have shown that the lattice energy of ammoniates is the sum of the two energies, namely the lattice energy of the ammonia free salts and the heat of formation of the ammoniates. In this present investigation, help has been taken from Biltz and Grim's work. Lattice energies of anhydrous fluoborates (U_1) were determined by two equations of Kapustiniskii⁵ and Yatsimirskii⁷. The values of lattice energies (U_2) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	U_1 , K cal/mole	Q K cal/mole	U_2 , K cal/mole
Co(BF_4) ₂ 2 Morpho	508.3	23.16	531.46
Co(BF_4) ₂ 1 Morpho	508.3	11.10	519.40
Cu(BF_4) ₂ 2 Morpho	504.66	32.90	537.46
Cu(BF_4) ₂ 1 Morpho	504.66	16.03	520.69
Zn(BF_4) ₂ 2 Morpho	493.0	22.72	515.72
Zn(BF_4) ₂ 1 Morpho	493.0	9.62	502.62
Co(BF_4) ₂ 2 Dioxan	508.3	34.83	543.13
Co(BF_4) ₂ 1 Dioxan	508.3	18.33	526.63
Ni(BF_4) ₂ 2 Dioxan	510.5	38.39	548.89
Ni(BF_4) ₂ 1 Dioxan	510.5	23.37	533.87
Cu(BF_4) ₂ 2 Dioxan	504.66	26.00	530.66
Cu(BF_4) ₂ 1 Dioxan	504.66	14.00	518.66
Zn(BF_4) ₂ 2 Dioxan	493.0	26.30	519.30
Zn(BF_4) ₂ 1 Dioxan	493.0	12.52	505.52

It is found in all the cases that as the number of ligand molecules decreases in a particular metal complex, the lattice energy value also decreases. It seems that as the number of ligands increases the crystal becomes more densely packed and hence the lattice energy value increases.

Similarly the lattice energy value decreases when the number of ligand molecules decreases as the crystal now becomes less densely packed.

References

1. A. CHATTERJI and G. C. BHATTACHARVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**(1), 38.
2. G. C. BHATTACHARVA and A. CHATTERJI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 135.
3. G. C. BHATTACHARVA, H. C. DASGUPTA and F. A. CHATTERJI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 1039.
4. G. C. BHATTACHARVA and H. C. DASGUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 157.
5. A. F. KAPUSTINISKII, *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, **10**, 283.
6. W. BILTZ and H. G. GRIM, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1935, **145**, 63.
7. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII, *J. Gen. Chem. USSR*, 1947, **17**, 2019.

TLC Separation of Some Inorganic Ions on Silica Gel-Ceric Molybdate Impregnated Layers

S. P. SRIVASTAVA, V. K. DUA

and

KAMLESH GUPTA

Chemical Laboratories, University of Roorkee, Roorkee, India

Manuscript received 12 June 1978, revised 4 December 1978,

accepted 12 March 1979

RECENTLY Malik and coworkers¹, have reported the ion-exchange behaviour of ceric molybdate. In the present study, we have utilised the ion-exchange property of ceric molybdate for the TLC separation of some closely related inorganic ions.

TABLE 1

Metal ion	$R_f^a \times 100$						Detection limit (in% w/v)	Colour of the spots
	Plain Silica gel		Impregnated layers					
	Solvent A	Solvent B	Solvent A		Solvent B			
Reference			Mixture	Reference	Mixture			
Group I								
Co(II) (Nitrate)	0	0	53	53	58	58	0.025	Violet
Zn (Acetate)	03	05	81	84	87	87	0.025	Dark pink
Cr (Chloride)	0	0	18	18	23	22	0.075	Green
Ni(II) (Sulphate)	0	0	49	48	52	51	0.075	Green
Al (Chloride)	—	—	31	31	34	34	0.075	Pinkish yellow
Cu(II) (Sulphate)	05	12	80	80	83	83	0.05	Chocolate
Sn(IV) (Chloride)	0	0	62	61	64	63	0.05	Yellowish orange
Fe(II) (Sulphate)	07T	08T	70	70	72	72	0.025	Light blue
Group II								
As(III) (Oxide)	16T	26T	29	29	31	31	0.05	Light yellow
Pb(II) (Acetate)	0	0	60	60	64	64	0.05	Yellow
Sb (Chloride)	30T	32T	56	55	61	60	0.05	Orange
Hg(IV) (Chloride)	14	26	95	95	95	95	0.025	Yellow
Cd (Nitrate)	0	0	73	73	78	78	0.05	Yellowish orange
Ag (Nitrate)	0	0	51	50	53	52	0.05	Black
Se (Dioxide)	44T	45T	65	65	69	69	0.025	Yellow

a = The values are average of two identical runs.
 (-) = not visualised.
 T = Tailing.

Experimental

Preparation of Ceric Molybdate : Ceric molybdate was prepared by mixing ammonium molybdate (0.05M) and ceric ammonium nitrate (0.05M) at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$). The initial pH of the ceric solution was adjusted with sulphuric acid. The precipitate in contact with liquid was left overnight at room temperature. It was then filtered, washed first with dilute sulphuric acid and then with deionised water and dried.

The TLC plates (thickness 0.5 mm) were prepared by spreading a slurry of a mixture of 50 g of silica gel G and 1.0 g of ceric molybdate (200 mesh) in 100 ml of distilled water and drying for 24 hrs at a constant temperature of 45° .

The inorganic ions (0.1% w/v solution in water) were applied to the layers using glass capillary and the chromatograms were eluted at constant temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ$) with a mixture of benzene-ethyl acetate-acetic acid-HCl (60 : 30 : 10 : 0.5) solvent A or (60 : 30 : 10 : 1.0) solvent B. After development the plates were sprayed with 0.5% dithiazone in chloroform. Results are shown in Table 1. For comparison sake, the chromatographic behaviour of these metal ions on plain silica gel is also given. It may be noted that on plain silica gel a streak of HCl (used in solvent system) is formed a little above the base line which hinders the movement of most of the metal ions and thus prevents their separation.

It is found that a satisfactory separation is obtained on impregnated plate if the ions are

divided into two groups. Further it is seen that for ions of Group I, solvent B is a better solvent system while for ions of Group II, solvent A is more suitable. It is significant to observe that the R_f value does not alter appreciably when the ions are present in mixture. As expected the R_f value in solvent B, which is more polar, are greater than those in solvent A.

Reference

1. W. U. MALIK, S. K. SRIVASTAVA and SATISH KUMAR, *J. Radio. anal. Chem.*, 1977, 40, 7.

Physico-chemical Studies on Weak Charge-transfer Complexes. I. Complexation of Phthalic Anhydride with Naphthalene

B. K. SEAL*, HARIDEB SIL

Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University,
Burdwan, West Bengal

and

D. C. MUKHERJEE

Eye Research Institute of Retina Foundation, 20, Staniford Street, Boston, Mass-02114, U.S.A.

THE unsaturated anhydrides¹⁻³ such as maleic and some substituted maleic anhydrides (MA and S-MA), tetrahalophthalic anhydrides, pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA), trimellitic anhydride, etc., are known, to form molecular complexes with π - and n -electron donors. The unsubstituted phthalic